

Some Halogeno-dinitrophenylhydrazines and their Condensation Products

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The present investigation is an extension of the work published earlier by one of the authors¹ and includes preparation of 2-fluoro- and 2-iodo-4,6-dinitrophenylhydrazines. These have been obtained by the interaction of 2-fluoro-1-chloro- and 1-chloro-2-iodo-4,6-dinitrobenzene², respectively, with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol.

The structure of the nitrophenylhydrazines follows from their methods of preparation. The hydrazones have been prepared by the usual methods.

As 2-fluoro-4,6-dinitrophenylhydrazine is soluble in common organic solvents and its solid derivatives having sharp melting points crystallise better than the corresponding 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones, we find that it is superior to 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine as a reagent for the identification of carbonyl compounds.

2-Fluoro-4,6-dinitrophenylhydrazine.—To a solution of 2-fluoro-1-chloro-4,6-dinitrobenzene³ (4.4g.) in ethanol (20 ml) a 50% hydrazine hydrate solution (5 ml) was added dropwise with vigorous shaking, maintaining the temperature at about 40°, and left overnight. The solution was concentrated to half of its volume under reduced pressure. On keeping for 2 hours, the 2-fluoro-4,6-dinitrophenylhydrazine separated. This was washed well with water and then crystallised from dilute ethanol in dark brown needles (2.5 g.), m.p. 111°. (Found: N, 25.81. C₆H₅O₄N₄F requires N, 25.92%.)

2-Iodo-4,6-dinitrophenylhydrazine.—A solution of 1-chloro-2-iodo-4,6-dinitrobenzene (4 g.) in ethanol (20 ml) and a 50% hydrazine hydrate solution (3.5 ml) were boiled for 5 minutes. On cooling, 2-iodo-4,6-dinitrophenylhydrazine separated as a solid which crystallised from acetic acid in dull yellow crystals (2.8 g.), m. p. 176°. (Found: I, 39.31. C₆H₅O₄N₄I requires, I, 39.16%). It is sparingly soluble in most of the common organic solvents.

Preparation of Phenylhydrazones.—Hydrazones were obtained in nearly quantitative yields by boiling for 4 to 5 minutes a mixture of a nitrophenylhydrazine (0.5 g.) in ethanol (5 ml) and the carbonyl compound in equimolecular proportion in presence of 1 to 2 drops of H₂SO₄ (conc.). The product was crystallised from ethanol.

Characteristics of the hydrazones prepared are shown in Table I.

1. Joshi and Deorha, *this Journal*, 1961, 28, 34; 1962, 29, 46; 1967, 34, 14.
2. Sane and Joshi, *ibid.*, 1932, 9, 60.
3. Deorha and Sharma, *ibid.*, 1963, 40, 973.

TABLE I

Carbonyl compounds.	2-Fluoro derivatives.				2-Iodo derivatives.			
	M.P.	Colour.	%Nitrogen.		M.P.	Colour.	%Iodine.	
			Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.
Formaldehyde	134°	Brownish yellow	24.41	24.56	157°	Dirty brown	37.49	37.76
Acetaldehyde	118°	Yellowish red	23.31	23.14	102°	„	36.62	36.25
Benzaldehyde	214°	Orange	18.19	18.42	235°	Orange	30.56	30.79
Salicylaldehyde	248°	Orange-red	17.61	17.49	252°	Orange-red	29.79	29.64
Anisaldehyde	229°	Red	16.61	16.76	240°	Red	28.62	28.70
Cinnamic aldehyde	207°	Vermilion-red	16.08	16.06	245°	Scarlet-red	29.19	28.96
Heliotropin	240°	Crimson-red	16.28	16.09	262°	„	26.19	27.53
Vanillin	249°	Deep violet	16.23	15.99	265°	Red	27.48	27.70
o-Vanillin	241°	Orange-red	16.21	15.99	237°	Pale yellow	27.43	27.70
m-Nitrobenzaldehyde	225°	Red	20.29	20.05	285°	Yellow	27.51	27.76
Acetone	103°	Light red	22.06	21.87	120°	Dirty brown	34.77	34.66
Methyl ethyl ketone	73°	Brownish yellow	20.54	20.73	109°	„	33.81	33.56
Acetophenone	191°	Red	17.77	17.61	234°	Orange	29.91	29.79
Benzophenone	187°	Light orange	14.49	14.73	235°	„	25.64	25.99

The authors' sincere thanks are due to Dr. R. C. Mehrotra, Professor and Head of the Chemistry Department, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, for providing facilities.

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Received September 25, 1963.